

Global Path Planning for Mobile Robots with Different Risk Metrics

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Abstract—This work proposes a method to include risk awareness in selecting the global path for a mobile robot moving in an environment shared with humans. We proactively consider prior information on human density distribution in the environment and the potential severity of an encounter in a particular location. We compute a graph considering one path candidate for each possible route in the environment. Each edge has a deterministic cost given by its average length, and a stochastic cost that depends on the number of people encountered while the robot moves on it and the severity of each encounter. Then, we plan on the obtained stochastic graph using different coherent risk metrics (Expected Cost, Worst Case, and Conditional Value at Risk), so that the robot can choose the best path according to the risk sensitivity of the specific application scenario.

Index Terms—Risk-aware global planner, risk metrics, path planning

I. INTRODUCTION

In risk management, risk is defined as an uncertain event that negatively impacts task success, and it is measured with a combination of probability and severity [1]. In confined spaces, encounters between robots and humans can cause stress for the human operator or even collisions and safety issues. Therefore, if an encounter happens, autonomous robots need to slow down and replan the trajectory online to avoid the human, with the possibility of stopping if a safe path is not found. This behavior can cause delays and performance degradation that vary according to the nature of the robot’s task.

In this work, we focus on human encounters as a source of risk, recognizing that the number and location of people in the environment are uncertain, and the severity of potential encounters varies depending on where they occur.

Risk-aware navigation usually studies the probability of collisions along a path locally, considering uncertainty in the environment sensing and robot state [3], [5]. We will instead study the problem at a higher level, investigating the best path the robot should choose to minimize the impact of replanning in case an encounter happens.

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The task the robot is performing influences the risk aversion level to adopt. When performing regular collecting and deployment operations the objective may be to maximize performances on average. If there is a strict deadline, instead, like when the robot has to go to pick up an object arriving from a conveyor belt, it may be convenient to use more conservative risk metrics to select the best path. In this work, we will consider three widely used risk metrics in robotics [7]: Expected Cost (EC), Conditional Value at risk (CVar), and Worst Case (WC).

The main contribution of this work is to study at the global path planning level how to treat and minimize the risk originating from potential human-robot encounters. We show how the path solution differs using different coherent risk metrics.

II. METHOD

A. Stochastic graph definition

When determining the minimum-risk global path, we are not interested in finding the exact trajectory the robot will follow, as it can be easily locally modified online (e.g., to perform evasive maneuvers and avoid the person encountered). As paths in the same constrained space (e.g., a corridor) will degrade together in case of human presence, we will group them. Therefore, we create a graph having as edges the corridors in the environment, and as vertices the intersection points between such corridors. To compute such a graph, and select the single candidate for each corridor to be used to compute the associated geometric properties, we use the generalized Voronoi diagram of the environment [6]. To compute the risk due to human encounters we assess encounters probability and severity in the environment.

1) *Encounters Probability*: We consider having information on people’s distribution in the environment. We define a unit segment u (e.g., $1m$), and we use it to discretize the curvilinear abscissa of our graph, rounding each edge length to an integer number $n_u \in \mathbb{N}$ of unit segments. We will assume the probability p_d that each segment is occupied as an input of our problem, and constant on each edge. If it’s not, a new node can be added to the graph every time p_d changes. Assuming that the presence of a person in each segment is independent of the presence of people in the rest of the environment, the probability of encountering k people while traversing the edge e would be:

$$p_k[e] = \binom{n_u}{k} p_d^k (1 - p_d)^{(n_u - k)}.$$

Path	EC	CVar	WC
EC path	81.43	134.91	273.48
CVar path	82.30	132.43	278.64
Worst Case Path	93.55	138.07	232.74

TABLE I: Path costs for 50000 simulations.

Fig. 1: **1a)** Map of the environment, colors represent the human presence probability in the area. **1b)** Resulting graph and paths according to the studied risk metrics. The robot moves between nodes 14 (in orange) and 15 (in green).

2) *Encounters Severity*: In this work, we consider encounter severity as linear dependent on the corridor’s width. We insert in our graph a new node each time the corridor width changes. In this way, we will have constant encounter severity in each resulting edge. We compute edge severity as:

$$c_p = \max(5, \min(-k_1(w_c - w_r) + k_2, k_3)),$$

where w_c denotes the width of the corridor, and w_r the robot’s width. The coefficients should be selected based on the specific application context, including factors like the robot’s mass, target speed, and the familiarity of humans with the robot. With this formulation, the severity coefficient for each corridor ranges from 5 to k_3 . This severity aims to represent the time in seconds that the robot may lose by slowing down or stopping to enable safe and effective local replanning.

The cost c_e of each edge would be: $c_e = l_e + n_e c_p$, where l_e is the edge length and n_e the number of encounters in that edge.

B. Planning with different risk metrics

As we consider edge costs as independent, the expected cost metric and worst case are additive. Therefore, we can compute the paths minimizing such metrics simply by computing the expected cost and worst case for each edge and finding the minimum path on the obtained deterministic graphs (for example, by using the A* algorithm with Euclidean distance as heuristic). CVar [7], instead, is not additive even for independent edge costs. However, the problem of finding the path that minimizes the CVar in a stochastic graph can be written as a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem, as described in [4]. To implement this method, we must generate a number N of scenarios representing edge cost realizations according to the probabilities defined before.

III. RESULTS

The method has been implemented in Python. We construct the Voronoi diagram from a picture of the environment using the code available in [6]. The MILP problem is implemented using the Pyomo software [2] with the “gurobi” solver. The CVar-optimal path is calculated based on the results from 1500 scenarios, using $\alpha = 0.9$ as the quantile to select

the worst 10% of cases. We tested our approach using the map in Fig. 1a. People density varies in the environment: $p_{dgreen} = 0.02, p_{dyellow} = 0.035, p_{dred} = 0.05$. The parameters for severity computation are: $k_1 = 15, k_2 = 65, k_3 = 50, w_r = 1m$. Fig. 1b reports the three paths obtained minimizing the Expected Cost (purple), CVar (green), and worst-case (red) risk metrics on the stochastic graph. We then tested the results obtained by running 50000 simulation scenarios. Table I reports the EC, CVar, and WC of the costs distribution over the simulations for the three paths. Results show that in this scenario the more risk-sensitive metrics prefer paths where the probability of making encounters is higher, but the associated severity is lower (wider corridors).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

Using different risk metrics, we have presented a method to minimize risk in the offline path selection.

Future works will include dynamically learning human distribution in the environment, and modeling the possible observations the robot will make at intersection points in the offline path selection problem.

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